

Binary classification measures for random approximate sets

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Abstract

We derive the probability distributions, expected values, and variances of standard binary classification measures—positive predictive value (precision), negative predictive value, accuracy, the f_1 -score, and Youden’s J statistic—for the Bernoulli set model, a compositionally closed framework for random approximate sets with independent, element-wise errors. The expected PPV and f_1 -score are obtained via second-order delta method expansions whose accuracy we validate by Monte Carlo simulation. All measures depend critically on the *prevalence* (base rate): even a small false positive rate can drive precision to zero when the base rate is low. The results apply to any data structure satisfying the Bernoulli axioms, including Bloom filters and perfect hash filters.

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1 Introduction

Binary classification measures—precision, recall, accuracy, F-score—are fundamental to evaluating information retrieval systems and probabilistic data structures. When a data structure approximates a set, returning membership queries that may err, the standard measures become random variables whose distributions depend on the error model. This paper derives those distributions within the Bernoulli set model [8], a compositionally closed probabilistic framework for random approximate sets with independent, element-wise errors parameterized by false positive and false negative rates.

Motivation. In many applications the question is not “what is the false positive rate?” but rather “given a positive test result, what is the probability it is correct?” This is the positive predictive value (precision), and its answer depends critically on the prevalence (base rate) of positives. A Bloom filter [1] with a 1% false positive rate achieves near-perfect precision when queried against a large positive set, but its precision collapses when positives are rare—a phenomenon well known in medical testing but underappreciated in the data structures literature.

Contribution. We derive exact distributions, closed-form approximations, and variances for PPV, NPV, accuracy, the f_1 -score, and Youden’s J within the Bernoulli set model [8]. The expected PPV and f_1 -score are obtained via second-order delta method expansions (theorems 3.1 and 3.4), and their accuracy is validated by Monte Carlo simulation (figs. 3 and 4). We show that all measures are functions of four parameters: the false positive rate ε , the true positive rate τ , the number of positives p , and the number of negatives n .

Related work. Fawcett [3] provides an introduction to ROC analysis; Powers [6] gives a systematic comparison of evaluation measures. The underlying Bernoulli set model and its compositional algebra are developed in a companion paper [8]; here we focus exclusively on the classification measures that the model induces.

Organization. Section 2 restates the Bernoulli axioms and the binomial distributions of error counts. Section 3 derives the distributions of PPV, NPV, accuracy, Youden’s J , and the f_1 -score. Section 4 concludes. Appendix A gives the full delta-method proof for expected PPV, Appendix B gives the proof for the f_1 -score, and Appendix C develops the sampling distribution framework.

2 Preliminaries

We briefly restate the elements of the Bernoulli set model [8] needed in this paper.

Axiom 1 (Element-wise independence). *For all distinct $x, y \in U$, the error events at x and y are mutually independent:*

$$P(\mathbf{1}_{\bar{A}}(x) \neq \mathbf{1}_A(x) \mid \mathbf{1}_{\bar{A}}(y) \neq \mathbf{1}_A(y)) = P(\mathbf{1}_{\bar{A}}(x) \neq \mathbf{1}_A(x)). \quad (2.1)$$

More generally, the family $\{\mathbf{1}_{\bar{A}}(x) : x \in U\}$ is mutually independent given the objective set A and the error rates. Furthermore, within each partition block B_i , the error indicators $\{\mathbf{1}_{\bar{A}}(x) : x \in B_i\}$ are identically distributed.

Proposition 2.1. *By axiom 1, for any single element $x \notin A$, $P(\mathbf{1}_{\bar{A}}(x) = 1) = \varepsilon$, and for $x \in A$, $P(\mathbf{1}_{\bar{A}}(x) = 1) = \tau$. The expected sample rates satisfy $E[\alpha] = \varepsilon$ and $E[\beta] = \tau$.*

Proof. See [8]. □

Theorem 2.1. *The random number of false positives FP given $N = n$ in the second-order random approximate set $\tilde{R}[\varepsilon]$ is given by*

$$FP_n = n\alpha \quad (2.2)$$

with a distribution given by

$$FP_n \sim \text{Bin}(n, \varepsilon). \quad (2.3)$$

Proof. See [8]. □

Theorem 2.2. *The random false positive rate α conditioned on $N = n$ is denoted by α_n and has a distribution given by*

$$\alpha_n = \frac{\text{FP}_n}{n}, \quad (2.4)$$

with an expectation ε , variance $\varepsilon(1 - \varepsilon)/n$, and probability mass function

$$p_{\alpha_n}(\hat{\varepsilon}|\varepsilon) = p_{\text{FP}_n}(\hat{\varepsilon}n|\varepsilon) \quad (2.5)$$

over the support $\{\frac{j}{n} \in \mathbb{Q} \mid j \in \{0, \dots, n\}\}$.

Proof. See [8]. □

Corollary 2.2.1. *Given n negatives, the number of true negatives in a random approximate set with a false positive rate ε is a random variable denoted by TN_n with a distribution given by*

$$\text{TN}_n = n - \text{FP}_n \sim \text{Bin}(n, 1 - \varepsilon). \quad (2.6)$$

By definition, the true negative rate $\text{TNR}_n = \text{TN}_n/n = 1 - \alpha_n$.

Proof. See [8]. □

Theorem 2.3. *Given p positives, the uncertain number of false negatives in random approximate sets with a false negative rate ω is modeled as a binomial distributed random variable denoted by FN_p ,*

$$\text{FN}_p \sim \text{Bin}(p, \omega). \quad (2.7)$$

Proof. See [8]. □

Corollary 2.3.1. *Given p positives, the number of true positives in an approximate set with a false negative rate ω is a random variable denoted by TP_p with a distribution given by*

$$\text{TP}_p \sim \text{Bin}(p, \tau). \quad (2.8)$$

By definition, the true positive rate is given by $\mathcal{T}_p = 1 - \beta_p$.

Proof. See [8]. □

3 Binary classification measures

When a random approximate set A^\pm replaces an objective set A , any function of the membership query results becomes a random variable whose distribution is inherited from the binomial error counts of section 2. Binary classification measures—positive predictive value, negative predictive value, accuracy, the f_1 -score, and Youden’s J —are such functions. These measures are standard in binary classification and information retrieval; see Fawcett [3] for an introduction to ROC analysis and Powers [6] for a systematic comparison of evaluation measures.

We derive expected values and variances for each measure. Since PPV, NPV, and the f_1 -score are nonlinear ratios of binomial random variables, their expectations require the delta method (a Taylor expansion about the means); accuracy and Youden’s J , being linear combinations, admit exact closed-form moments. The accuracy of *predictions* about objective sets given a corresponding approximate set is usually the more relevant performance measure. The *positive predictive value* is given by the following definition.

Figure 1: Relative frequency of positive predictive values for several different parameterizations of the false positive and true positive rates given $n = 900$ negatives and $p = 100$ positives.

Definition 3.1. *The positive predictive value is a performance measure defined as*

$$\text{ppv} = \frac{t_p}{t_p + f_p} \quad (3.1)$$

where t_p is the number of true positives and f_p is the number of false positives.

The positive predictive value of random approximate sets is a random variable given by the following theorem.

Theorem 3.1. *Given n negatives, p positives, and a random approximate set with false positive and true positive rates ε and τ respectively, the positive predictive value is a random variable*

$$\text{PPV} = \frac{\text{TP}_p}{\text{TP}_p + \text{FP}_n} \quad (3.2)$$

with an expectation given approximately by the second-order delta method [2] (a Taylor expansion of $\text{E}[\text{TP}_p / (\text{TP}_p + \text{FP}_n)]$ about the means, valid when $p\tau$ and $n\varepsilon$ are both large; the error is $\mathcal{O}(1/\min(p, n)^2)$)

$$\text{ppv}(\tau, \varepsilon, p, n) \approx \frac{\bar{t}_p}{\bar{t}_p + \bar{f}_p} + \frac{\bar{t}_p \sigma_{f_p}^2 - \bar{f}_p \sigma_{t_p}^2}{(\bar{t}_p + \bar{f}_p)^3}, \quad (3.3)$$

where $\bar{t}_p = p\tau$ is the expected true positive frequency, $\bar{f}_p = n\varepsilon$ is the expected false positive frequency, $\sigma_{t_p}^2 = (1 - \tau)\bar{t}_p$ is the variance of the true positive frequency, and $\sigma_{f_p}^2 = (1 - \varepsilon)\bar{f}_p$ is the variance of false positive frequency. The first-order delta method variance is

$$\text{Var}(\text{PPV}) \approx \frac{\bar{f}_p^2 \sigma_{t_p}^2 + \bar{t}_p^2 \sigma_{f_p}^2}{(\bar{t}_p + \bar{f}_p)^4}. \quad (3.4)$$

See section A for a proof of theorem 3.1.

We make the following observations about eq. (3.3):

Figure 2: Expected precision (positive predictive value) as a function of the false positive rate ε for a positive Bernoulli set ($\omega = 0$) at three prevalences $\lambda = p/(p + n)$. Even a small false positive rate dramatically reduces precision when the base rate is low.

1. For sufficiently large approximate sets, $\text{ppv} \approx \bar{t}_p/(\bar{t}_p + \bar{f}_p)$.
2. If $\varepsilon \neq 0$, as $n \rightarrow \infty$, $\text{ppv} \rightarrow 0$.
3. As $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$, $\text{ppv} \rightarrow 1$.

Accuracy is given by the following definition.

Definition 3.2. *The accuracy is the proportion of true results (both true positives and true negatives) in the universe of positives and negatives, $(t_p + t_n)/(p + n)$, where t_p , t_n , p , and n are respectively the number of true positives, true negatives, positives, and negatives.*

The *expected accuracy* is given by the following theorem. Let $\lambda = p/(p + n)$ denote the *base rate* (proportion of positives).

Theorem 3.2. *Given p positives and n negatives, the accuracy of a random approximate set with an expected false positive rate ε and an expected true positive rate τ is a random variable given by*

$$\text{ACC}_{p+n} = \lambda \text{TPR}_p + (1 - \lambda) \text{TNR}_n \quad (3.5)$$

with an expected accuracy

$$\text{acc}(\tau, \varepsilon, n, p) = \lambda \tau + (1 - \lambda) \eta \quad (3.6)$$

and a variance

$$\frac{\lambda \omega \tau + (1 - \lambda) \varepsilon \eta}{p + n}. \quad (3.7)$$

Proof. Suppose the u elements in the universe can be partitioned into p positives and n negatives. An approximate set \tilde{S} with a false positive rate ε and false negative rate ω has an uncertain accuracy

$$\text{ACC}_{p+n} = \frac{\text{TP}_p + \text{TN}_n}{p + n}. \quad (\text{a})$$

Figure 3: Comparison of theoretical expected PPV (eq. (3.3), dashed) with Monte Carlo simulation (circles, $N = 50\,000$ trials per point) for a positive Bernoulli set ($\omega = 0$) with prevalence $\lambda = 1\%$ ($p = 100$, $n = 9900$). The theoretical curve and simulation points are indistinguishable, validating the second-order Taylor approximation.

The expected accuracy is given by the expectation

$$\mathbb{E} [\text{ACC}_{p+n}] = \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{\text{TP}_p + \text{TN}_n}{p+n} \right] \quad (\text{b})$$

$$= \frac{p(1-\omega) + n(1-\varepsilon)}{p+n}. \quad (\text{c})$$

Noting that $n/(p+n) = 1 - p/(p+n)$ and letting $\lambda = p/(p+n)$,

$$\mathbb{E} [\text{ACC}_{p+n}] = \lambda(1-\omega) + (1-\lambda)(1-\varepsilon). \quad (\text{d})$$

The variance

$$\text{Var} (\text{ACC}_{p+n}) = \text{Var} \left(\frac{\text{TP}_p}{p+n} \right) + \text{Var} \left(\frac{\text{TN}_n}{p+n} \right) \quad (\text{e})$$

$$= \frac{1}{(p+n)^2} \text{Var} (\text{TP}_p) + \frac{1}{(p+n)^2} \text{Var} (\text{TN}_n) \quad (\text{f})$$

$$= \frac{p\omega(1-\omega)}{(p+n)^2} + \frac{n\varepsilon(1-\varepsilon)}{(p+n)^2} \quad (\text{g})$$

$$= \frac{\lambda\omega\tau + (1-\lambda)\varepsilon\eta}{p+n}. \quad (\text{h})$$

□

Definition 3.3. *The negative predictive value is a performance measure defined as*

$$\text{npv} = \frac{t_n}{t_n + f_n} \quad (3.8)$$

where t_n and f_n are respectively the number of true negatives and false negatives.

The expected negative predictive value is given by the following theorem.

Theorem 3.3. *Given p positives, n negatives, and a random approximate set with false positive and true positive rates ε and τ respectively, the negative predictive value is a random variable*

$$\text{NPV} = \frac{\text{TN}_n}{\text{TN}_n + \text{FN}_p} \quad (3.9)$$

with an expectation given approximately by

$$\text{npv}(\tau, \varepsilon, p, n) \approx \frac{\bar{t}_n}{\bar{t}_n + \bar{f}_n} + \frac{\bar{t}_n \sigma_{f_n}^2 - \bar{f}_n \sigma_{t_n}^2}{(\bar{t}_n + \bar{f}_n)^3}, \quad (3.10)$$

where $\bar{t}_n = n(1 - \varepsilon)$ is the expected true negative frequency, $\bar{f}_n = p(1 - \tau)$ is the expected false negative frequency, $\sigma_{t_n}^2 = \varepsilon \bar{t}_n$ is the variance of the true negative frequency, and $\sigma_{f_n}^2 = \tau \bar{f}_n$ is the variance of the false negative frequency. The first-order delta method variance is

$$\text{Var}(\text{NPV}) \approx \frac{\bar{f}_n^2 \sigma_{t_n}^2 + \bar{t}_n^2 \sigma_{f_n}^2}{(\bar{t}_n + \bar{f}_n)^4}. \quad (3.11)$$

The proof for theorem 3.3 follows the same pattern as the proof for theorem 3.1.

Youden's J statistic is a measure of the performance of a binary test, defined as

$$J = \frac{t_p}{t_p + f_n} + \frac{t_n}{t_n + f_p} - 1, \quad (3.12)$$

with a range $[-1, 1]$. In the case of the random approximate set model, J is a random variable

$$J = \text{TPR}_p - \alpha_n, \quad (3.13)$$

which has an *expectation*

$$\text{E}[J] = \tau - \varepsilon \quad (3.14)$$

and, by the independence of TPR_p and α_n , a *variance*

$$\text{Var}(J) = \frac{\tau \omega}{p} + \frac{\varepsilon \eta}{n}. \quad (3.15)$$

3.1 The f_1 -score

Definition 3.4. *The f_1 -score is the harmonic mean of precision and recall:*

$$f_1 = \frac{2t_p}{2t_p + f_p + f_n}. \quad (3.16)$$

Since $f_n = p - t_p$, the f_1 -score may be written as a function of t_p and f_p alone:

$$f_1 = \frac{2t_p}{t_p + f_p + p}. \quad (3.17)$$

Theorem 3.4. Given p positives, n negatives, and a random approximate set with false positive and true positive rates ε and τ respectively, the f_1 -score is a random variable

$$F_1 = \frac{2 \text{TP}_p}{\text{TP}_p + \text{FP}_n + p} \quad (3.18)$$

with an expectation given approximately by the second-order delta method

$$\mathbb{E}[F_1] \approx \frac{2\bar{t}_p}{\bar{t}_p + \bar{f}_p + p} + \frac{2\bar{t}_p\sigma_{f_p}^2 - 2(\bar{f}_p + p)\sigma_{t_p}^2}{(\bar{t}_p + \bar{f}_p + p)^3} \quad (3.19)$$

and a first-order delta method variance

$$\text{Var}(F_1) \approx \frac{4(\bar{f}_p + p)^2\sigma_{t_p}^2 + 4\bar{t}_p^2\sigma_{f_p}^2}{(\bar{t}_p + \bar{f}_p + p)^4}, \quad (3.20)$$

where $\bar{t}_p = p\tau$, $\bar{f}_p = n\varepsilon$, $\sigma_{t_p}^2 = p\tau(1-\tau)$, and $\sigma_{f_p}^2 = n\varepsilon(1-\varepsilon)$.

See section B for a proof of theorem 3.4.

Figure 4: Comparison of theoretical expected f_1 -score (eq. (3.19), dashed) with Monte Carlo simulation (circles, $N = 50\,000$ trials per point) for a positive Bernoulli set ($\omega = 0$) with prevalence $\lambda = 1\%$ ($p = 100$, $n = 9900$). The theoretical curve and simulation points are indistinguishable, validating the second-order delta method approximation.

Table 1 may be used to reparameterize an approximate set.

Example 1 Suppose we seek a positive approximate set with an expected accuracy γ . By table 1,

$$\gamma = \text{acc}(\varepsilon, \omega = 0, \lambda) = 1 - \varepsilon(1 - \lambda). \quad (a)$$

Solving for ε in terms of γ yields the result

$$\varepsilon(\gamma, \lambda) = \frac{1 - \gamma}{1 - \lambda} \quad (b)$$

Table 1: Various *expected* performance measures.

measure	parameter	expected value
true positive rate	$\text{tpr}(\tau)$	τ
false positive rate	$\text{fpr}(\varepsilon)$	ε
false negative rate	$\text{fnr}(\tau)$	$1 - \tau$
true negative rate	$\text{tnr}(\varepsilon)$	$1 - \varepsilon$
accuracy	acc	eq. (3.6)
positive predictive value	ppv	eq. (3.3)
negative predictive value	npv	eq. (3.10)
f_1 -score	f_1	eq. (3.19)
false discovery rate	fdr	$1 - \text{ppv}$
false omission rate	for	$1 - \text{npv}$

subject to $0 \leq \lambda \leq \gamma \leq 1$ and $\lambda < 1$. Under this parameterization of the positive approximate set, λ must be known (or estimated). Note that if $\lambda = 1$ then $\varepsilon(\gamma, \lambda = 1)$ is undefined as expected, but as λ goes to 1, $\varepsilon(\cdot; \lambda)$ goes to 1 and γ goes to 1, which logically follows since if there are no negatives, there can be no false positives.

3.2 Interval-valued classification measures

When the error rates or the proportion of positives are not known exactly, interval arithmetic [9, 4, 5] may be applied: each uncertain parameter is replaced by an interval guaranteed to contain its true value, and the classification-measure formulas are evaluated over these intervals to produce guaranteed bounds.

Example 2 (Interval accuracy) Suppose we wish to determine the expected accuracy given that the proportion of positives λ is known to be some value in the interval $[\lambda]$, and that the false positive and false negative rates lie in $[\varepsilon]$ and $[\omega]$ respectively. The accuracy formula $\text{acc} = \lambda(1 - \omega) + (1 - \lambda)(1 - \varepsilon)$ may be rewritten as

$$\text{acc} = (1 - \varepsilon) + \lambda(\varepsilon - \omega). \quad (\text{a})$$

Since the accuracy is multilinear in $(\varepsilon, \omega, \lambda)$, its extremes over the box $[\varepsilon] \times [\omega] \times [\lambda]$ are attained at vertices. The formula is decreasing in ε and ω , but its monotonicity in λ depends on the sign of $\varepsilon - \omega$:

- If $\varepsilon \geq \omega$ (the common case, e.g., Bloom filters), accuracy increases in λ , so:

$$\text{acc} \in \left[(1 - \bar{\varepsilon}) + \underline{\lambda}(\bar{\varepsilon} - \bar{\omega}), (1 - \underline{\varepsilon}) + \bar{\lambda}(\underline{\varepsilon} - \underline{\omega}) \right]. \quad (\text{b})$$

- If $\varepsilon < \omega$, accuracy decreases in λ , so the λ endpoints are reversed:

$$\text{acc} \in \left[(1 - \bar{\varepsilon}) + \bar{\lambda}(\bar{\varepsilon} - \bar{\omega}), (1 - \underline{\varepsilon}) + \underline{\lambda}(\underline{\varepsilon} - \underline{\omega}) \right]. \quad (\text{c})$$

In practice, guaranteed bounds are obtained by evaluating the accuracy at all $2^3 = 8$ vertices and taking the minimum and maximum.

Example 3 (Interval PPV) Given interval-valued rates, the positive predictive value inherits interval bounds. Since $\text{ppv} \approx \bar{t}/(\bar{t} + \bar{f})$ for large sets (theorem 3.1), substituting $\bar{t} = p\tau$ and $\bar{f} = n\varepsilon$ and evaluating at the extremes of $[\varepsilon]$ and $[\tau]$ yields

$$[\text{ppv}] \approx \left[\frac{p\underline{\tau}}{p\underline{\tau} + n\bar{\varepsilon}}, \frac{p\bar{\tau}}{p\bar{\tau} + n\underline{\varepsilon}} \right], \quad (\text{a})$$

providing guaranteed bounds on the expected precision under uncertain rates.

4 Conclusion

We have derived the probability distributions, closed-form expected values, and variances of the principal binary classification measures—positive predictive value, negative predictive value, accuracy, the f_1 -score, and Youden’s J statistic—for the Bernoulli set model. In each case the measure is a random variable whose distribution follows from the binomial error counts established by the element-wise independence axiom (axiom 1). The expected PPV and f_1 -score were obtained via second-order delta method expansions (theorems 3.1 and 3.4), and their accuracy was validated by Monte Carlo simulation (figs. 3 and 4).

These results apply to any data structure satisfying the Bernoulli axioms, including Bloom filters [1] and perfect hash filters [7]. In particular, the sensitivity of PPV to prevalence (fig. 2) has practical implications for system design: a data structure with a nominally small false positive rate may still produce unreliable positive predictions when the base rate of positives is low. Designers should therefore evaluate their systems not only by FPR and FNR but also by the predictive values that the intended query workload will induce.

Several directions remain open. First, the distribution of the Matthews correlation coefficient (MCC) under the Bernoulli model has not been derived in closed form; it involves a more complex ratio of binomial random variables than PPV or f_1 . Second, extension to correlated error models—where the element-wise independence axiom is relaxed—would broaden the applicability of the framework to data structures with dependent hash functions or adversarial inputs. Finally, the interplay between prevalence and the higher-order composition algebra of [8, 9] deserves further study: as approximate sets are composed through union and intersection, the effective prevalence at each stage changes, and so do the classification measures.

A Proof of theorem 3.1

Given p positives and n negatives, by theorem 3.1 an approximate set with a false positive rate ε and a false negative rate ω has an *expected* precision given *approximately* by

$$\text{ppv}(\omega, \varepsilon; n, p) \approx \frac{\bar{t}}{\bar{t} + \bar{f}} + \frac{\bar{t}\sigma_f^2 - \bar{f}\sigma_t^2}{(\bar{t} + \bar{f})^3}, \quad (\text{3.3 revisited})$$

where $\bar{t} = p\tau$ is the *expected* number of *true positives*, $\bar{f} = n\varepsilon$ is the *expected* number of *false positives*, $\sigma_t^2 = p\omega\tau$ is the variance of the number of *true positives*, and $\sigma_f^2 = n\varepsilon\eta$ is the variance of the number of *false positives*.

Proof. The positive predictive value is a random variable given by

$$\frac{\text{TP}_p}{\text{TP}_p + \text{FP}_n}. \quad (\text{a})$$

We are interested in the *expected* positive predictive value,

$$\text{ppv}(\varepsilon, \tau) = \text{E} \left[\frac{\text{TP}_p}{\text{TP}_p + \text{FP}_n} \right]. \quad (\text{b})$$

This expectation is of a non-linear function of random variables, which is problematic so we choose to approximate the expectation.

Let the *positive predictive value* function be denoted by

$$f(t, f) = \frac{t}{t + f}, \quad (\text{c})$$

where t is the number of true positives and f is the number of false positives. We approximate this function with a second-order Taylor series. The gradient of f is given by

$$\nabla f(t, f) = \frac{1}{(t + f)^2} \begin{bmatrix} f \\ -t \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{d})$$

and the Hessian of f is given by

$$\mathcal{H}(t, f) = \frac{1}{(t + f)^3} \begin{bmatrix} -2f & t - f \\ t - f & 2t \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{e})$$

A second-order Taylor approximation g of f about the expected value of TP_p , denoted by \bar{t} , and the expected value of FP_n , denoted by \bar{f} , is given by

$$g(t, f) = f(\bar{t}, \bar{f}) + \nabla f(\bar{t}, \bar{f})^\top \begin{bmatrix} t - \bar{t} \\ f - \bar{f} \end{bmatrix} + \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} t - \bar{t} \\ f - \bar{f} \end{bmatrix}^\top \mathcal{H}(\bar{t}, \bar{f}) \begin{bmatrix} t - \bar{t} \\ f - \bar{f} \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{f})$$

As a function of random variables TP_p and FP_n , $g(\text{TP}_p, \text{FP}_n)$ is a random variable. Since $\text{E}[\text{TP}_p - \bar{t}] = 0$ and $\text{E}[\text{FP}_n - \bar{f}] = 0$, we immediately simplify the expectation of g to

$$\text{E}[g(\text{TP}_p, \text{FP}_n)] = \frac{\bar{t}}{\bar{t} + \bar{f}} + \frac{\text{E}[A]}{(\bar{t} + \bar{f})^3} \quad (\text{g})$$

where

$$A = \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} \text{TP}_p - \bar{t} \\ \text{FP}_n - \bar{f} \end{bmatrix}^\top \begin{bmatrix} -2\bar{f}(\text{TP}_p - \bar{t}) + (\bar{t} - \bar{f})(\text{FP}_n - \bar{f}) \\ (\bar{t} - \bar{f})(\text{TP}_p - \bar{t}) + 2\bar{t}(\text{FP}_n - \bar{f}) \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{h})$$

Expanding the quadratic form yields

$$A = -\bar{f}(\text{TP}_p - \bar{t})^2 + (\bar{t} - \bar{f})(\text{TP}_p - \bar{t})(\text{FP}_n - \bar{f}) + \bar{t}(\text{FP}_n - \bar{f})^2 \quad (\text{i})$$

As a linear operator, the expectation of A is equivalent to

$$\text{E}[A] = -\bar{f}\text{E}[(\text{TP}_p - \bar{t})^2] + (\bar{t} - \bar{f})\text{E}\left[(\text{FP}_n - \bar{f})(\text{TP}_p - \bar{t})\right] + \bar{t}\text{E}[(\text{FP}_n - \bar{f})^2] \quad (\text{j})$$

By definition, $\text{E}[(\text{TP}_p - \bar{t})^2]$ is the variance of TP_p , $\text{E}[(\text{FP}_n - \bar{f})^2]$ is the variance of FP_n , and $\text{E}\left[(\text{FP}_n - \bar{f})(\text{TP}_p - \bar{t})\right]$ is the covariance of TP_p and FP_n , which is 0 since they are independent. Making these substitutions results in

$$\text{E}[A] = \bar{t}\text{Var}(\text{FP}_n) - \bar{f}\text{Var}(\text{TP}_p) \quad (\text{k})$$

Substituting this result into eq. (g) yields

$$\mathbb{E} [g(\text{TP}_p, \text{FP}_n)] = \frac{\bar{t}}{\bar{t} + \bar{f}} + \frac{-\bar{f}\text{Var}(\text{TP}_p) + \bar{t}\text{Var}(\text{FP}_n)}{(\bar{t} + \bar{f})^3} \quad (l)$$

By theorem 2.1, FP_n is binomially distributed with a mean $n\varepsilon$ and a variance $n\varepsilon\eta$ and by corollary 2.3.1, TP_p is binomially distributed with a mean $p\tau$ and a variance $p\omega\tau$. Substituting $\text{Var}(\text{FP}_n) = n\varepsilon(1 - \varepsilon) = \bar{f}(1 - \varepsilon) = \sigma_f^2$ and $\text{Var}(\text{TP}_p) = p\tau(1 - \tau) = \bar{t}(1 - \tau) = \sigma_t^2$ yields eq. (3.3).

For the variance, the first-order delta method gives $\text{Var}(\text{PPV}) \approx (\nabla f)^\top \Sigma (\nabla f)$ with $\Sigma = \text{diag}(\sigma_t^2, \sigma_f^2)$:

$$\text{Var}(\text{PPV}) \approx \frac{\bar{f}^2 \sigma_t^2 + \bar{t}^2 \sigma_f^2}{(\bar{t} + \bar{f})^4}, \quad (m)$$

which yields eq. (3.4). \square

B Proof of theorem 3.4

The proof follows the same structure as the PPV proof (section A) with the substitution $h(t, f) = 2t/(t + f + p)$ in place of $f(t, f) = t/(t + f)$.

Proof. The f_1 -score is a random variable $F_1 = h(\text{TP}_p, \text{FP}_n)$ where

$$h(t, f) = \frac{2t}{t + f + p}. \quad (a)$$

The gradient of h is

$$\nabla h(t, f) = \frac{2}{(t + f + p)^2} \begin{bmatrix} f + p \\ -t \end{bmatrix} \quad (b)$$

and the Hessian is

$$\mathcal{H}(t, f) = \frac{2}{(t + f + p)^3} \begin{bmatrix} -2(f + p) & t - f - p \\ t - f - p & 2t \end{bmatrix}. \quad (c)$$

The second-order Taylor expansion about the means $\bar{t} = p\tau$, $\bar{f} = n\varepsilon$, letting $s = \bar{t} + \bar{f} + p$, gives

$$\mathbb{E} [h(\text{TP}_p, \text{FP}_n)] \approx h(\bar{t}, \bar{f}) + \frac{1}{2} \text{tr}(\mathcal{H}(\bar{t}, \bar{f}) \Sigma) \quad (d)$$

where $\Sigma = \text{diag}(\sigma_t^2, \sigma_f^2)$ and the cross terms vanish by independence. Expanding:

$$\frac{1}{2} \text{tr}(\mathcal{H} \Sigma) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{-4(\bar{f} + p)}{s^3} \sigma_t^2 + \frac{4\bar{t}}{s^3} \sigma_f^2 \right) = \frac{2\bar{t} \sigma_f^2 - 2(\bar{f} + p) \sigma_t^2}{s^3}. \quad (e)$$

Adding $h(\bar{t}, \bar{f}) = 2\bar{t}/s$ completes the expected-value formula.

For the variance, the first-order delta method gives $\text{Var}(F_1) \approx (\nabla h)^\top \Sigma (\nabla h)$:

$$\text{Var}(F_1) \approx \frac{4(\bar{f} + p)^2 \sigma_t^2 + 4\bar{t}^2 \sigma_f^2}{s^4}. \quad (f)$$

Substituting $\sigma_t^2 = p\tau(1 - \tau)$ and $\sigma_f^2 = n\varepsilon(1 - \varepsilon)$ yields eqs. (3.19) and (3.20). \square

C Sampling distribution of arbitrary functions

Suppose we have a function $f : 2^{X_1} \times \dots \times 2^{X_q} \rightarrow Y$, and we are interested in evaluating the loss when we replace one or more of the objective input sets with particular corresponding random approximate sets. The result of this substitution, as previously described, is a probability distribution over Y .

The probability distribution of random approximate sets are precisely given; therefore, we may estimate the distribution of any function of random approximate sets by generating the random approximate sets and applying the function of interest.

Consider the m -by- q matrix where the (i, j) -th element is the random approximate set $\tilde{A}_{i,j}$ such that each random element of the matrix is independently and each column is identically distributed. If we apply g to each row of the matrix,

$$Y_i = g(\tilde{A}_{i,1}, \dots, \tilde{A}_{i,q}) \quad (\text{C.1})$$

for $i = 1, \dots, m$, we generate m i.i.d. random elements Y_1, \dots, Y_m .

If Y is a measure space (discrete or continuous), consider the random variable

$$\bar{Y}_m = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m Y_i. \quad (\text{C.2})$$

If Y_1 has a well-defined mean $\mu = E[Y_1]$ and variance $\sigma^2 = \text{Var}(Y_1)$, then by the central limit theorem

$$\sqrt{m}(\bar{Y}_m - \mu) \xrightarrow{d} \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2) \quad (\text{C.3})$$

as $m \rightarrow \infty$. That is, for large m the sample mean \bar{Y}_m is approximately normally distributed with mean μ and variance σ^2/m .

This framework underlies the Monte Carlo validation of the delta method approximations in figs. 3 and 4: for each parameter value, $m = 50\,000$ independent random approximate sets are generated, and the sample mean of the measure is compared to the theoretical prediction. The large sample size ensures that the Monte Carlo standard error is negligible relative to the quantities being estimated.

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